

**A multi-level framework and an assessment toolbox to guide the
transformation journey towards sustainable zero-defect manufacturing**

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive framework, and an assessment toolbox aimed to assist manufacturing companies in navigating their transformation journey toward sustainable zero-defect manufacturing. Specifically, they support assessment and decision-making across strategic, tactical, and operational levels, and incorporate a balanced consideration of key manufacturing competitive priorities, including economic, environmental, social, and innovation aspects. In doing so, the paper contributes to advance current research and practice on sustainable zero-defect manufacturing by offering an integrated approach and toolbox that facilitate alignment of technical innovations with organizational needs and sustainability outcomes.

Keywords: zero-defect manufacturing, ZDM, assessment, maturity model, sustainability, eco-efficiency, multi-layer value stream mapping, task, skill.

1 Introduction

Zero-Defect Manufacturing (ZDM) is *“a holistic approach for ensuring both process and product quality by reducing defects through corrective, preventive, and predictive techniques, using mainly data-driven technologies and guaranteeing that no defective products leave the production site and reach the customer, aiming at higher manufacturing sustainability”*(CEN-CELEC, 2022).

ZDM is expected to impact multiple performance dimensions (Antony et al., 2022), to have a lasting effect on cost reduction and waste elimination (Psarommatis et al., 2022), and a net-positive environmental impact (Fragapane et al., 2023). The ZDM paradigm closely aligns with sustainability objectives by reducing waste, optimizing resource use, and improving operational efficiencies (Psarommatis et al., 2022; Psarommatis & Azamfirei, 2024).

By integrating ZDM and sustainability assessments, companies can quantify ZDM contributions to economic, environmental and social performance, ensuring that its adoption drives meaningful progress toward smart and sustainable manufacturing. However, according to recent literature reviews, studies that analyse the performance implications of ZDM and measure the impact on KPIs are still very rare (Caiazzo et al., 2022; Powell et al., 2022; Psarommatis et al., 2020).

Existing approaches tend to focus on isolated aspects without providing a comprehensive framework for integration across management levels and time horizons. Without such a multi-level framework and set of tools tailored for ZDM transformation, companies often lack coherence in their transformation efforts, resulting in fragmented initiatives that fail to deliver lasting results (Psarommatis et al., 2022; Psarommatis & Azamfirei, 2024). A well-defined framework, complemented by a practical toolbox, is therefore crucial for enabling companies to systematically and effectively achieve sustainable ZDM.

To contribute to filling the above-mentioned gap, a multi-level and multi-dimensional assessment framework including a suite of tools was created and tested in the FLASH-COMP project to support manufacturing companies during the planning and assessment phases of their transformation journey toward sustainable ZDM.

According to its objective, the remainder of the paper is structured as follows: the research method is outlined in Section 2; the multi-level assessment framework and the toolbox are described in Section 3; finally, Section 4 concludes the paper by summarizing its implications, limitations and future research directions.

2 Methodology

To develop the framework and related assessment tools, insights from academic literature were combined with the expert knowledge of partners involved in the FLASH-COMP project.

First, the literature review aimed to identify key factors critical for the successful adoption of ZDM and potential impacts of ZDM on multiple performance dimensions. From the literature review, main assessment methods were selected – i.e., 1. maturity assessment model, 2. process flow analysis and multi-layer value stream mapping, 3. task and skill gap analysis - and the related data collection and analysis tools were designed and developed considering the ZDM context. These methods and artifacts were then presented, discussed, and refined collaboratively with the project partners through an iterative process. This approach ensured that the framework, along with its associated toolbox, is grounded in robust scientific knowledge while being tailored to address the practical needs of companies.

Second, the assessment tools were applied in the two industrial companies involved in the FLASH-COMP project, which operate in the yachting and aerospace industries. The overall analysis of the two industrial cases helped in better understanding the current challenges and opportunities for improvement through the implementation of ZDM. Data were collected in collaboration with the representatives from both companies, and the assessment results were shared with them. This also allowed for an analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of each tool. Finally, lessons learned and recommendations for future implementation were elaborated.

3 Results and discussion

Error! Reference source not found. shows the overall structure of the framework and related assessment tools. The framework consists of three levels and four pillars. The three levels – i.e., strategic, tactical and operational level - closely resemble the production planning levels commonly adopted in manufacturing companies, while the four pillars – i.e., operational/economic, environmental, human/social, digital and data innovation - emphasizing four performance categories (Rybicka et al., 2015; Jitpaiboon et al., 2016; Pinzone et al., 2020). A detailed description of each tool is provided in the following paragraphs.

Figure 1. Multi-level assessment framework and related tools.

3.1 Strategic Level: The Zero-Defect Manufacturing Maturity Model

The Strategic level is focused on the production system (e.g., plant, etc.) and oriented towards the long term. This level focuses on establishing the strategic objectives and direction required to advance towards ZDM. This involves identifying long-term measures, aligning them with organizational vision and mission, and defining the framework to guide the transition towards ZDM (Pachimuthu et al., 2024).

To this end, a ZDM maturity model was specifically developed as a comprehensive tool to encapsulate and assess all the critical ZDM socio-business-technical factors. As detailed in (Pinzone et al., 2025), the ZDM maturity model's structure includes five maturity levels and six dimensions: Product, Process, Platform, People, Partnership, and Performance. Each dimension is populated with several ZDM-related factors (Figure 2) that ascertain comprehensiveness and completeness in terms of assessing the maturity towards adopting ZDM. The maturity levels, as portrayed in (Table 1), serves as the scale of evaluation, with each level representing the capability and advancement towards achieving defect-free manufacturing.

The ZDM maturity assessment is conducted through an online self-assessment questionnaire followed by direct interviews of the industry experts. This dual approach helps identify the current maturity level and the targeted profile for ZDM implementation. The assessment results are then visualized using radar charts, which provide a clear depiction of the company's profile and facilitate discussions about the implications for the company.

Overall, the ZDM maturity assessment serves as a foundation for creating a tailored roadmap that addresses multiple dimensions and harmonizes their interactions. This ensures that companies not only adopt ZDM systems but also integrate them into their broader industrial strategy, paving the way for sustainable and scalable implementation.

PRODUCT DIMENSION	PROCESS DIMENSION	PLATFORM DIMENSION	PEOPLE DIMENSION	PARTNERSHIP DIMENSION	PERFORMANCE DIMENSION
Customisation	Process management	Inspection instruments and sensors			Operational
Integration of Sensors/Actuators	QMS - Quality controls	Asset Administration Shell (AAs)	ZDM business strategy	Research and innovation	Economic
Communication/ connectivity	QMS – Level of inspection	Vertical interoperability of data and events	ZDM culture and organisation	Training and education	Environmental
Data storage and exchange of information	QMS - Procedures	Industrial data platform	People management – Competencies	IT solution providers	Social
Monitoring	QMS - Data analysis of quality checks	Digital twin	People management – Ergonomics & working conditions	Suppliers	Customer satisfaction
Smart traceability	Risk Management System	Data analytics	People management – Employee Engagement	Customers	Product-service lifecycle
Smart servicing	Standardised tool or methods of intervention	Human Machine Interface	People management – Rewards	Industrial data sharing agreements	Supply chain
	ZDM strategies	Tracking system			Data performance
		Horizontal interoperability of data and events			
		Data space			

Figure 2. ZDM Maturity Factors categorized in 6 dimensions

Table 1. ZDM Maturity Levels

Maturity Level	Short description
1) Initial	Little awareness or minimally acceptable effort in ZDM.
2) Managed	Initiation of shift towards proactive measures aimed at identifying and addressing root causes of defects before they impact product quality.
3) Defined	Integration of various departments/ processes towards quality control.
4) Integrated	Organization fully integrates ZDM processes into its culture and operations.
5) Exploited	ZDM is recognized as part of the organization’s culture and becomes a source of long-term competitive advantage for the business.

3.2 Tactical Level

The Tactical level is focused on the processes within the organisation and more oriented toward the medium term. Accordingly, the assessment at this level is aimed at thorough depiction of the workflow, encompassing the machinery involved, and the specific human skills required to ensure smooth operation.

3.2.1 Process efficiency and eco-efficiency assessment

A multi-tool methodology was developed to conduct the assessment of efficiency and eco-efficiency in manufacturing processes (E J Lourenço et al., 2013). Integrating the assessment of both efficiency and eco-efficiency offers a comprehensive approach for the detailed characterization of process performance.

This includes process flow analysis, to distinguish value-added and non-value-added activities, and Multi-layer Stream Mapping methodology (Castiglione et al., 2024; Emanuel J Lourenço et al., 2016) to assess the performance of the process in several domains – i.e., operational, resources costs and environmental - providing a global overview of the process efficiency.

Figure 3. Representation of data collection and assessment process.

Finally, the eco-efficiency analysis integrates the costs derived from cost analysis with the assessment of environmental impacts, being assessed using costs and life cycle inventory data. In this way, the eco-efficiency analysis highlights sustainability aspects that yield greater value through reduced material and energy inputs and emissions.

The data collection and assessment are carried out via a structured excel file, following the diagram presented in Figure 3, which enables the industry representatives to input the process data and visualize the efficiency and eco-efficiency results. The results can be obtained in two stages, first by implementing MSM, a scorecard with process efficiency estimation is generated. Then, by combining the cost assessment conducted using MSM with environmental impact assessment, the normalized eco-efficiency for each process can be calculated.

3.2.2 Task and skill gap assessment

Following Koripadu & Subbiah, 2014; Kim & Ji, 2018, the task and skill gap assessment is divided into three sequential phases: I. detection, II. anticipation, and III. validation. These phases are executed according to a defined timeline as represented in Figure , ensuring that both industrial stakeholders and digital solution providers contribute their insights and expertise in a coordinated and consistent manner.

Phase I starts with the compilation of a list of relevant jobs and corresponding tasks at the industrial site. Company representatives are asked to answer two key questions for each listed task: first, whether the task will be affected by the new ZDM system (Yes or No); second, for the affected tasks, what specific skills are currently required to perform them before the ZDM system is implemented.

Based on the findings from Phase I, each affected task is broken down into its individual steps and list the tools currently used to perform each step. Partners must categorize the impact of the envisioned solution as either "Stop" (if the step will no longer be performed), "Change" (if the step will be modified), or "Remain unchanged" (if the step will continue as it is).

Phase III incorporates the technical team’s perspective, ensuring that the analysis performed by the industrial partners is validated and refined with a technical viewpoint. This phase helps to ensure the feasibility of the anticipated changes.

This method is designed to generate two critical insights that are essential for facilitating a smooth transition toward ZDM. First, it is expected to uncover workflow adaptations due to ZDM solution implementation, fostering worker engagement and minimizing resistance to change. Second, it enables a detailed mapping of skill requirements for each task, aiding in targeted upskilling programs.

Figure 4. Proposed method for task and skill gap assessment

3.1 Operational Level

The Operative level is focused on the single piloting test to be performed at the shopfloor, and it is oriented towards the short term. At this level, the focus is on deployment and testing specific ZDM solutions in factory environment. At this stage validation protocols are designed by detailing the resources and activities required to pilot testing the ZDM system, collect data and assess the expected KPI improvements. These activities include preparing the experimental setup, defining key metrics, collecting data, analysing performance, and assessing the feasibility and scalability of the solution under evaluation.

3.2 Implementation in FLASH-COMP

Table 2. Key evidence from pilot implementation Table 2 provides a summary of the key insights gained from implementing the toolbox in the two industrial companies involved in the FLASH-COMP project. It highlights the strengths of each proposed assessment tool, the primary challenges encountered during the pilot phase with industrial companies, the lessons learned, and recommendations for future use and improvements.

Table 2. Key evidence from pilot implementation

Tool	Strengths	Challenges	Lesson learned and recommendations
ZDM Maturity assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☞ The ZDM maturity model offers a holistic and comprehensive assessment. ☞ It can be used across various industries, as demonstrated in aerospace and yachting applications. ☞ Hosted through an online questionnaire, the assessment is easily accessible and facilitates straightforward data analysis. ☞ Each factor focuses on a specific aspect, ensuring the transferability of analysis into actionable insights. ☞ It facilitates the match of solutions with specific ZDM aspects and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * It requires multiple respondents and cross-functional collaboration. * Qualitative answers can be affected by subjectivity, being overly optimistic or pessimistic. * Contextual and interpretational differences can mislead analysis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☞ Provide detailed instructions and familiarize respondents with the questions before completing the questionnaire. ☞ Provide support during the online questionnaire compilation and/or organize interviews and company visits to collect data. ☞ Evaluate the possibility to link maturity levels with quantitative KPIs to increase objectivity.

Efficiency and Eco- efficiency assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☞ This approach can assess, quantify and analyse environmental impact adding economic and productions dimensions one by one for each unit process. ☞ The use of dimensionless ratios allows the comparison of efficiency performance of distinct variables, and combine an integrated quantification of the overall efficiency, for instance by weighted average or product. ☞ The outcome and results are a diagrammatical and intuitive representation of managerial concepts and can be very practical and useful. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Data collection is a complex process, since not all the parameters and variables are recorded and monitored by the use cases. * It is an iterative process that takes time in order to define how the KPIs can be collected, representing effectively the process efficiency. * The MSM requires the comparison between target values and measured values which increases the complexity of the approach. * Data coming from the environmental impact are based on assumptions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☞ The target values are difficult to quantify, and the reference values highly depends on the product. ☞ Considering the complexity of the process, several data are difficult to be quantified, and some assumptions needs to be made in order to understand the environmental, operational and cost impact of each process. ☞ This approach identifies the process that induce the higher costs and environmental impact, allowing use cases to optimize the process steps.
Task and skill gap assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☞ It provides detailed insights at the site, job, task, and step levels. ☞ It uses percentages and task counts for objective impact assessment. ☞ It allows direct comparison of transformation across job roles. ☞ It supports designing effective support measures based on specific needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Detailed, multi-level analysis and support planning are time and resource intensive. * Some roles and tasks are heavily impacted, requiring significant workforce adaptation. IT might lead to resistance to change. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☞ Continuous communication management is essential to ensure the smooth operation of this multi-phase method.

4 Conclusion

The paper introduces a comprehensive framework and toolbox that spans strategic, tactical, and operational management levels, integrating four dimensions to address socio-technical, environmental, and economic performance. This structured, multi-level, and multi-dimensional approach aims to achieve sustainable ZDM. It contributes to addressing the research gap identified by Konstantinidis et al. (2023) and Maganga & Taifa (2023), and to offer a practical toolbox for companies striving to achieve both operational excellence and sustainability in ZDM practices.

The development of this toolbox marks a significant stride toward operationalizing ZDM. By integrating the ZDM maturity readiness, process efficiency assessment, and gap assessment, it puts forward a cohesive framework that guides manufacturers in identifying improvement areas and aligning strategies toward ZDM. However, the current study has certain limitations. The proposed framework and toolbox were developed through theoretical methods thus far and were only preliminarily validated in two industrial cases. Therefore, their large-scale deployment and validation in real-world manufacturing settings remain areas for future research.

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